

If Large Language Models (LLMs) hallucinate, do they also dream electric sheep?

Mind and machine semantic drifts: on the misuse of psychopathological language in the age of language models

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Abstract:

The widespread use of psychiatric terms like “hallucination” and “psychosis” to describe the behavior of large language models (LLMs), while undeniably sensationalistic, is both conceptually misleading and semantically imprecise. Hallucinations, in their clinical and phenomenological sense, presuppose an incarnated subjectivity and a disrupted self-world structure, none of which LLMs possess. At the same time, this semantic drift risks trivializing severe mental illness by equating complex experiential disturbances with statistical output errors. While “confabulation” offers a somewhat closer analogy, it too remains an inadequate approximation. Anthropomorphic language in AI discourse distorts our understanding of both minds and machines. Terminological precision is not pedantic, but rather ethically and epistemologically necessary.

Key words:

Large Language Models (LLMs), AI hallucinations, anthropomorphism in AI, psychiatric terminology, confabulation, AI ethics, mental health stigma, phenomenology of psychosis, machine learning errors, terminological precision

Key points :

- Labeling AI errors as “*hallucinations*” is both scientifically misleading and ethically hazardous.
- Psychiatric terms like “*hallucination*” falsely ascribe human features (e.g., selfhood, intentionality) to LLMs, which lack consciousness.
- “*Confabulation*” is a descriptively closer (but still flawed) approximation.
- Precise language is critical to avoid trivializing mental illness (e.g., equating psychosis with algorithmic glitches) while accurately represent AI’s statistical, non-agential nature.

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“Our environment – and I mean our man-made world of machines, artificial constructs, computers, electronic systems, interlinking homeostatic components – all of this is in fact beginning more and more to possess what the earnest psychologists fear the primitive sees in his environment: animation. In a very real sense our environment is becoming alive, or at least quasi-alive, and in ways specifically and fundamentally analogous to ourselves... Rather than learning about ourselves by studying our constructs, perhaps we should make the attempt to comprehend what our constructs are up to by looking into what we ourselves are up to.”

Philip K. Dick, "The Android and the Human" (1972)

As Dick suggests, our proclivity to see animation where none exists reflects more about human cognition than machine behavior. This anthropomorphic tendency has not only shaped public perceptions of AI but has bled into technical and even medicalized language. It is here that the metaphor of “hallucination” begins to blur the line between linguistic behavior and lived experience, revealing the need for conceptual caution.

On the casual misuse of psychiatric language in AI and why it matters

In recent years, in both scientific and [mediatic](#) circuits, large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT and Claude have been described as “[hallucinating](#)” when they generate plausible but false information. As their linguistic sophistication grows, some have gone further, referring to these models as “psychotic,” or as producing “delusional” outputs. While these terms are catchy and headline-friendly, they carry conceptual baggage that is not just misleading and factually wrong but it is also ethically problematic.

What happens when we treat machine-generated anomalies as though they were symptoms of human mental illness? We risk flattening the rich terrain of psychiatric language, trivializing lived experiences of mental suffering, and confusing the public about what these systems are actually doing.

The problem with “Hallucination”

At first glance, it seems intuitive to say an LLM “hallucinates” when it produces a confident but false output. But this metaphor only works if we accept an extremely shallow definition of hallucination: “perception without external stimulus.”

In psychiatry, especially from a phenomenological perspective, hallucinations are far more complex. They involve a breakdown in the structure of selfhood, a disturbance in the relation between subject and world. The experience is involuntary, often terrifying, and deeply embedded in a person’s lived reality.

LLMs do not perceive. They do not have a world. They do not possess a self that can be invaded by alien phenomena. To say they hallucinate is to apply a word that presupposes subjectivity to systems that have none. It is a metaphor with no anchor.

It is understandable why the term gained traction: it’s vivid, intuitively graspable, allusively human and mimics the realism of model output. But this semantic shortcut comes at a cost: it imports clinical connotations that not only misrepresent the model’s operations, but also risk trivializing the lived complexity of psychiatric phenomena.

And what about psychosis?

The term “psychosis” has recently surfaced in AI discourse to describe especially erratic or contradictory model behavior. But psychosis, like hallucination, is not a mere output failure. It is an existential rupture. To be psychotic is not to say something strange, it is to lose one’s grip on reality, to undergo a radical transformation of consciousness, of self-experience, and of the way of being with other human beings.

When we call a machine psychotic, we do more than anthropomorphize. We risk equating deeply human forms of mental distress with computational unpredictability. This is not only conceptually flawed, but it is stigmatizing.

A better (but still imperfect) fit: confabulation

If we must borrow a psychiatric term, confabulation is closer to the mark. In neuropsychology, confabulation refers to the unintentional creation of false memories, e.g. plausible stories that fill in the gaps of damaged memory. It is not intentional deception, but compensation.

Human confabulation serves a compensatory function: it preserves discursive continuity in the face of memory failure or autobiographical disruption. By contrast, LLMs confabulate not to make sense of absence or loss, but as a byproduct of probabilistic token optimization—absent any anchoring subjectivity.

Similarly, when LLMs produce factually incorrect content, they are not lying or hallucinating. They are filling in gaps based on probability, coherence, and context. They are, in a sense, confabulating, albeit without memory or consciousness.

Still, even this term must be used carefully. Real confabulation involves a self trying to maintain coherence. LLMs have no such self. The metaphor is approximate, not exact.

Why language matters

Clearly, the mediatized success of psychiatric terminology in AI discourse reflects a double misunderstanding: first, the projection of animation and psychological traits onto LLMs, largely due to their discursive fluency and contextual reactivity; and second, the oversimplification of psychopathology through the widespread adoption of operational definitions that flatten clinical complexity.

Yet, words shape thoughts.

When we import psychiatric concepts into AI discourse, we risk distorting both domains. We obscure the true nature of artificial systems, and we trivialize the lived experience of mental illness. The metaphor may be seductive, but its simplicity is misleading.

Let us be terminologically precise, and resist the comforting collapse of machines (disembodied algorithms) and minds (incarnated beings) into one.

Because no matter how strange their outputs, LLMs do not hallucinate.

And no, they do not dream of electric sheep.

Further Reading

This reflection draws conceptually on classical psychopathology and phenomenological psychiatry (notably Sass, Parnas, Stanghellini, Fuchs and Raballo – See [PUBMED](#)), and culturally from Philip K. Dick's *The Android and the Human* (1972).